

An Eye-Controlled Wheelchair: Design of a Novel Human-Computer Interface(HCI) for Patients with Motor Neuron Disease By Arav Mehta

Abstract

By 2025, approximately 65 million people will be users of Electric Power Wheelchairs(EPW's), which significantly boost quality of life(NCBI). However, a challenge gone undocumented in academic research is that many patients are unable to use EPW joysticks due to a variety of impairments in motor function, sensation, or cognition. Therefore, it was decided that an EOG(electrooculography)-based mobility aid would allow users to control the wheelchair via eye signals collected from a pair of glasses consisting of 3 electrodes placed on the outer canthi and left mastoid. Signals were filtered using a 0.5 - 19.5 Hertz Butterworth filter, and interpreted by an adaptive thresholding detection algorithm. Wheelchair construction involved conversion of a manual wheelchair to motorized. The three subsystems, sensing, interpretation, and movement, were individually and holistically examined to conclude that the final product achieved a signal detection accuracy rate of ~89%, and ultimately achieved its goal of being the first everyday, cost-effective alternative to traditional EPW's.

Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Motor Neuron Disease

Motor neuron diseases (MNDs) are a group of progressive neurodegenerative disorders characterized by the selective loss of upper and/or lower motor neurons, leading to muscle weakness, spasticity, and eventual paralysis (Brown and Al-Chalabi). As voluntary motor control deteriorates, patients experience significant impairments in mobility, posture, and gait, often requiring the early transition from ambulatory aids to manual or powered wheelchairs for functional independence and reducing caregiver burden (van der Woude et al.). Advanced disease stages may necessitate alternative control interfaces—such as eye-tracking, sip-and-puff, or switch scanning—due to severe limitations in hand strength and dexterity. Consequently, wheelchair selection, customization, and ongoing adaptation play a central role in preserving quality of life for individuals with MND.

1.1.2 Electric Power Wheelchairs

Wheelchairs are essential mobility aids for people with varying levels of physical impairment, helping them navigate their environments and maintain independence, ultimately for the purpose of restoring a high quality of life. Wheelchairs include manual and powered types, each with distinct mechanisms for movement. Manual wheelchairs typically rely on the user's strength to propel them forward by pushing the wheels, while motorized wheelchairs, on the other hand, rely on electric motors to move the wheelchair. The user controls the movement using a joystick or other control interface, such as a sip-and-puff system(breath control) or a touchpad. The joystick can be used to control the direction (forward, backward, or turning), and in some cases, the speed.

1.1.3 Existing Wheelchair Control Systems

Recent research and development efforts have advanced the state of the art in eye-tracking and wheelchair control interfaces, yet significant challenges remain. For example, systems combining eye-tracker glasses with depth cameras and ultrasonic sensors have allowed users with ALS to safely drive a power wheelchair, while other approaches use video-based eye gaze detectors to steer via on-screen dwell points or blink commands. However, many existing solutions struggle to meet all practical requirements. Camera-based eye trackers often require frequent recalibration or a fixed head position, and their performance can degrade with changes in lighting or reflective eyewear; as a result, reliability in real-world conditions (e.g. response time, accuracy, and user comfort) remains inadequately demonstrated in the literature.

1.1.4 Electrooculography

Electrooculography (EOG) is a technique that quantifies ocular position and blink-related corneoretinal potential (CRP) changes by measuring voltage fluctuations generated between the positively charged cornea and negatively charged retina (Barea et al.). This standing potential creates a stable dipole whose orientation shifts with extraocular muscle activation; consequently, horizontal, vertical, and oblique eye movements produce characteristic voltage fluctuations detectable at the skin surface (Leitgeb et al.). For example, during horizontal eye movements, rotation of the ocular dipole causes the corneal pole to move closer to the electrode positioned toward the gaze direction, producing a proportional increase in measured potential, while the opposite electrode records a corresponding decrease (Picerno et al.). In contrast, blink events generate transient, high-amplitude artifacts resulting from rapid eyelid movement, mechanical electrode-skin deformation, and brief disruption of the corneal contribution to the dipole; these waveforms exhibit sharp, monophasic peaks that differ temporally and morphologically from voluntary saccades (Ferree et al.).

EOG acquisition commonly employs wet electrodes (typically Ag/AgCl electrodes) using chloride-containing electrolyte gels to reduce skin–electrode impedance and enhance signal fidelity (Chi et al.). In contrast, dry electrodes—constructed from conductive polymers, typically stainless steel, titanium, or gold-plated substrates—improve user comfort and long-term wearability but often exhibit higher impedance and greater susceptibility to motion noise (Berry et al.). Regardless of electrode type, standard polysomnographic and clinical practice adopts a three-electrode EOG configuration, in which two active electrodes are positioned approximately 1 cm lateral to the outer canthi to capture horizontal corneoretinal potential changes, while a reference electrode placed over the mastoid region provides a stable baseline for differential amplification consistent with AASM-recommended montage guidelines (Berry et al.).

Figure 1. Electrode placement for horizontal and vertical EOG. Adapted from Wojtczak-Kwaśniewska M, Przekoracka-Krawczyk A, Van der Lubbe RHJ. 2018. *Electrode placement for EOG data collection*, PLOS ONE. Licensed under CC BY 4.0. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0198405.g002>

1.2 Rationale and Scope

Independence in mobility is a fundamental goal of assistive technology for individuals with Motor Neuron Disease. For those affected by severe conditions, conventional wheelchair controls (e.g. hand joysticks or voice/sip-and-puff interfaces) may be unusable, leaving eye movement as one of the few viable means of interaction. Eye-tracking technology has thus emerged as a promising channel for restoring mobility in this context: by translating a user's gaze direction into wheelchair navigation commands, an eye-controlled interface can enable hands-free locomotion and significantly improve quality of life. Furthermore, electrooculography (EOG) was selected as the control modality due to its low latency, minimal computational requirements, and robustness to lighting conditions as compared to camera-based systems.

The overarching goal is to create a universally accessible mobility apparatus that is usable by a wide range of users and affordable in diverse settings. If successful, this prototype will offer a practical pathway for restoring independent mobility to users who can no longer operate conventional wheelchair controls, filling a critical gap in current assistive technology.

1.3 Research Objectives

The objective of this study is to design and evaluate a low-cost, non-invasive electrooculography-based human-machine interface that enables real-time electric wheelchair control for individuals with Motor Neuron Disease.

1.4 Roadmap

Section 2 describes the system architecture, hardware integration, and signal-processing methodology; Section 3 reports the accuracy, responsiveness, and performance results; Section 4 interprets these findings in relation to existing assistive-technology research; and Section 5 concludes with key contributions and directions for future development.

Materials and Methodology

2.1 System Overview and Requirements

The objective of this project was to develop an affordable, non-invasive, and eye-controlled electric wheelchair designed specifically for individuals with Motor Neuron

Disease (MND). To achieve this, the system integrates a low-cost EOG-based wearable device with a motorized wheelchair platform, enabling real-time, gaze-driven navigation without reliance on hand-operated joysticks or expensive commercial eye-tracking systems. The design was guided by the following goals of cost-effectiveness, functional reliability, and complete hardware–software integration:

- $\leq \$300$ — Total wheelchair build cost
- $\leq \$60$ — Total head-mounted EOG device cost
- ≥ 8 hours — Minimum system battery life
- ≤ 200 g — Maximum weight of wearable device
- ≥ 0.5 mph — Wheelchair minimum operating speed
- ≤ 1 second — End-to-end system response time
- $\geq 80\%$ — Minimum signal classification accuracy

2.2 Materials and Components

2.2.1 Wheelchair Platform

A standard manual wheelchair obtained from a local clinic served as the mechanical base for motorization. Two 24 V brushless DC motors were mounted to the rear axle (2 M10 bolts) using custom 3D-printed brackets (PETG-CF and PLA) and steel couplers. The frame modifications allowed the wheelchair to be converted into a powered platform without altering its structural integrity.

Figure 2. Rear-mount motor assembly using custom 3D-printed brackets and steel couplers to convert a manual wheelchair into a powered platform.

2.2.2 Power System

The powered wheelchair was driven by a 24 V, 7 Ah rechargeable deep-cycle lithium-ion battery, accompanied by a compatible 24 V charger. A DC-DC buck converter supplied regulated 5 V to the microcontrollers and control electronics.

2.2.3 Motor Driver and Control Electronics

An L298N dual H-bridge motor driver module controlled the left and right drive motors, receiving directional commands from the microcontroller. An Arduino Uno was used for initial testing and motor driver interfacing, while an ESP32 microcontroller handled high-level

communication and processing in the final prototype due to its low latency and dual-core architecture.

2.2.4 Supporting Hardware

Assorted wiring, screws, jumper connectors, and passive components were used for motor wiring, power distribution, and mechanical mounting. Additional fixtures, including 3D-printed housings (TPU, PETG-CF, PLA), supported the battery, electronics, and drivetrain components.

2.2.5 Eye-Tracking Glasses

Custom eye-tracking glasses were fabricated using a 3D-printed frame that housed the electronics and supported electrode placement. A BioAmp EXG Pill circuit board (analog front-end amplifier) was used to acquire and condition binocular EOG signals. An ESP32 microcontroller was integrated into the frame to achieve signal digitization and wireless transmission.

Figure 3. Internal electronics layout of the eye-tracking glasses, including BioAmp EXG amplifier, ESP32-C3 module, and battery compartment.

2.2.6 Glasses Power Supply

The glasses were powered by a set of three AAA alkaline cells connected in series to provide a nominal 4.5 V supply, with the batteries filling up the right side of the frame to maintain balanced weight distribution.

2.2.7 Electrodes

Three dry silver electrodes were used to acquire horizontal EOG signals. Dry silver electrodes were selected for their low baseline impedance relative to other dry sensor materials and their suitability for long-term wear, though they still required amplification and digital filtering to manage motion-related and technical (50/60 Hz power line interference) noise.

2.3 Hardware Assembly

2.3.1 Glasses Assembly

The glasses frame was fabricated as a hollow, compartmentalized 3D-printed structure with dedicated internal cavities for electronics and power distribution. The left temple housed the BioAmp EXG Pill analog front-end and the ESP32-C3 microcontroller responsible for signal digitization and wireless transmission. The right temple contained the 3 batteries to provide a balanced mass distribution across the frame. Two dry silver electrodes were embedded within the frame to be positioned 1 cm lateral to the outer canthi, while the reference electrode was routed externally on a small vertical attachment towards the mastoid placement site. Internal wiring channels were integrated directly into the print to improve aesthetics.

Figure 4. CAD rendering of the custom 3D-printed glasses frame used to house the electrodes, amplifier board, microcontroller, and onboard power supply.

2.3.2 Wheelchair Assembly

A manual wheelchair obtained from a local clinic was retrofitted with two 24 V brushless DC motors mounted to the rear axle using PETG-CF/PLA 3D-printed brackets and M10 steel bolts. Motor shafts were coupled to the wheel hubs using steel couplers, enabling powered motion without altering the wheelchair’s structural frame. A 24 V, 7 Ah lithium-ion battery and DC-DC buck converter supplied power to the drivetrain and control electronics. The L298N motor driver and the Arduino/ESP32 modules were mounted in 3D-printed housings secured to the frame, with wiring routed through protective conduits to prevent mechanical interference.

Figure 5. Wiring diagram of the powered wheelchair system showing the connections between the 24 V battery, DC-DC converter, L298N motor driver, dual brushless DC motors, and the microcontroller responsible for issuing directional control signals.

2.4 Biopotential Signal Processing

2.4.1 Signal Acquisition

For precise signal acquisition, two reusable, non-invasive dry silver/silver-chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrodes were embedded within a custom-designed, glasses-like plastic wearable. In accordance with AASM guidelines, the electrodes were positioned 1 cm lateral to the left and right outer canthi (known as IN+ and IN-), with a reference electrode placed on the left mastoid bone (known as REF).

2.4.2 Analog Signal Conditioning

The three electrode inputs—IN+, IN-, and REF—are first routed into the BioAmp EXG Pill hardware as an analog front-end, where the instrumentation amplifier performs the initial differential amplification and noise suppression before the subsequent digitization and filtering stages. The PCB's architecture comprises five key functional blocks: instrumentation amplification, electrode reference management, bandpass filtering with high gain, power supply conditioning, and a driven right leg (DRL) circuit for common-mode noise reduction.

1. **Instrumentation Amplifier (INA):** The first stage consists of a differential amplifier using an op-amp from the TL074H integrated circuit configured to amplify the voltage difference between two input electrodes. A second op-amp buffers the differential signal. The gain is configurable through a resistor network, and a 2.2 nF capacitor is placed across the inputs to suppress high-frequency noise.
2. **Electrode Configuration:** A solder jumper (JP1) allows selection between two- or three-electrode configurations, with the third electrode acting as a reference (ground) to improve signal stability.
3. **Bandpass Filter with Gain (~1000×):** The amplified differential signal is passed through a second-stage active bandpass filter, also built around a TL074H op-amp. The filter bandwidth can be adjusted via a solder jumper (JP2) to target narrow frequency bands. Additional passive elements allow further tuning of gain and center frequency.
4. **Power Supply Filtering:** The circuit is powered by a single-supply 5V source, with decoupling capacitors (100 nF and 4.7 μF) smoothing the rail to reduce supply ripple and transient noise.
5. **Driven Right Leg (DRL) Circuit:** To enhance common-mode rejection, a DRL stage is implemented using an additional op-amp to invert and feed back a portion of the common-mode signal into the body through the reference electrode. This minimizes environmental 50/60 Hz interference and stabilizes the baseline.
6. **Connectors and Output:** Standard header pins provide connectivity for the three input electrodes (IN+, IN-, DRL) and for a singular processed analog signal output. This output is later directly interfaced with a microcontroller for further signal processing.

2.4.3 Signal Digitization

The amplified and conditioned analog output from the BioAmp EXG module was digitized using the ESP32-C3 Mini's integrated 12-bit analog-to-digital converter (ADC). A timed acquisition loop, implemented using the ESP32-C3's internal millisecond timer, enforced a fixed sampling frequency of 75 Hz.

2.4.4 Tracking State Variables

Four state variables are consistently used to measure aspects of the system. The first is the gaze state variable, which stores the user's current horizontal eye position (LEFT, RIGHT, or NEUTRAL) and updates only when an eye blink or directional spike is detected. Because the filtered signal returns to zero during steady gaze in any direction, this persistent state variable is essential for maintaining an accurate representation of the user's absolute eye position between transitions, as opposing directional spikes can return the state to neutral (e.g. A RIGHT move detected while the gaze currently has a value of LEFT will set gaze to NEUTRAL). The second is the rapid blink tracker, a temporal counter that identifies cases where three or more blinks occur within a one-second window. Finally, the z_1 and z_2 state variables form the internal memory for each bi-quad section of the Butterworth IIR filter. These variables store intermediate values from previous samples, allowing the recursive filter to maintain stability and implement its designed frequency response.

2.4.5 Digital Filtering

A 4th-order Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) Butterworth band-pass filter was implemented to isolate relevant electrooculography (EOG) signals from low-frequency drift and high-frequency noise typically present in biopotential data. The EOGFilter() function, adapted from open-source code developed by Upside Down Labs for the BioAmp EXG Pill, was written in C++ for use on Arduino-based microcontrollers. Operating at a sampling rate of 75 Hz, the filter passes frequencies between 0.5 Hz and 19.5 Hz, which is standard for capturing eye movement signals (Berry et al.). It is structured as a cascade of four second-order sections (bi-quads), each maintaining internal state variables (z_1 , z_2) to enable recursive filtering. Additionally, the Infinite Impulse Response architecture was chosen over Finite Impulse Response specifically due to its low computational overhead, which is optimal for real-time signal processing. It is also important to note that the following interpretation techniques use only the filtered signal values, represented as x_i , which are no longer an analog (0-1023) value, but are rather variably scaled around a mean of 0.

2.4.6 Initial Calibration

An initial one-minute calibration period where the subject maintains neutral gaze is required before use to establish the individual baseline constant $\sigma_{baseline}$, or the standard deviation of resting-state noise in the absence of eye movements, using the formula

$$\sigma_{baseline} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{4.5 \cdot 10^3} \sum_{i=1}^{4.5 \cdot 10^3} x_i^2} .$$

2.4.7 Spike Detection

Theoretical spike detection employs the classification criterion $|x_i| > k_{\text{horizontal}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}}$, where $k = 3.0$, enabling identification of both irrelevant, saccadic eye movements and sustained eye position changes that deviate significantly from the personalized neutral gaze baseline.

2.4.8 Continuous Recalibration

While σ_{baseline} can reliably be used as in the short-term, the system implements five-minute recalibration intervals to address the well-documented baseline drift phenomenon in EOG recordings. The implemented algorithm employs a sliding context window approach containing 22,500 samples, recalculating a fresh σ_{baseline} every 5 minutes. During each recalibration window, normal spike detection criteria (using the previous σ_{baseline} statistic) is still used to exclude eye movement artifacts, ensuring that only neutral gaze samples contribute to calibrated baseline updates. To prevent baseline corruption from excessive eye movements or recording anomalies, the algorithm incorporates drift magnitude validation that restricts baseline updates to physiologically plausible ranges ($\pm 100 \mu\text{V}$ from the previous baseline). If baseline drift is detected to be invalid, the context window resets, and the system will require another initial calibration before further use.

2.4.9 Blink Detection

Following a positive result from the initial spike detection, a secondary filtering stage exploits the characteristic amplitude differences between the transient, saccadic eye movements and blinks to isolate spike events caused by blinking. Amplitude thresholds are derived from the baseline calibration data. Since blink events typically exceed a value 5-10 times the standard deviation of horizontal saccadic movements (σ_{baseline}), spike events surpassing the blink threshold $|x_i| > k_{\text{blink}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}}$, with $k_{\text{blink}} = 8.0$, are flagged as potential blinks and subjected to further temporal validation.

Additionally, while saccadic eye movements last between 20-40 milliseconds, blinks maintain a duration between 100-400 milliseconds on average. Using a sliding context window consisting of 30 samples, each value is labeled as either a potential blink or neutral value based on the previously established amplitude-based thresholding system. The context window is then evaluated using a majority vote system of 2 adjacent 15-sample windows within the larger context window. If either window returns a majority of potential blinks, the spike event is confirmed to be a blink, and the spike detection subsystem is disabled according to a 200 millisecond 'cooldown'.

2.4.10 Signal Classification

For non-spike events, horizontal eye movement direction is determined through signal polarity analysis with incorporated noise tolerance. Given the differential electrode configuration with left and right outer canthus placement, the algorithm employs a three-state classification system that accounts for signal variability near the baseline. Directional classification uses threshold-based criteria: leftward movements are identified when $x_i > +0.5 \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}}$, rightward movements occur when $x_i < -0.5 \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}}$, and a neutral/uncertain state for deviations within the dead zone where $-0.5 \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}} \leq x_i \leq +0.5 \cdot \sigma_{\text{baseline}}$. This dead zone approach prevents misclassification of minor baseline fluctuations, electrode noise, or small eye movements as

definitive directional commands while maintaining sensitivity to genuine horizontal eye movements.

2.4.11 Majority Vote Validation

The final processing stage implements a sliding window majority vote system using a 7-sample window (~93 milliseconds at 75 Hz) due to the somewhat transient nature of horizontal eye movements. For each time point, the algorithm examines the preceding 7 directional classifications and adjusts the state variable (gaze) based on the most frequent category within the window. Although the reduced window size prioritizes detection speed over blink artifact rejection, this is appropriate given that the primary objective is real-time horizontal movement tracking rather than comprehensive blink detection.

2.5 Motor Control

The ESP32-C3 module onboard the signal acquisition device acts as an access point for the wheelchair's ESP32, transmitting state-variable updates via WiFi at 75 Hz. Information from these state variables is converted into discrete motor commands and delivered to the L298N motor driver, which interfaces directly with the left and right drive motors. When the horizontal gaze state variable is classified as "left" or "right," the corresponding motor is slowed while the opposite motor is driven forward, producing a turning motion; when the state variable indicates "neutral," both motors receive equal forward torque, resulting in straight-line movement; and when a blink-based "stop" state is detected, both motors are immediately disabled to halt the wheelchair.

2.6 User Interface

The system incorporated a simple, gesture-based user interface that allowed the wheelchair to be activated, controlled, and stopped using only eye movements. To prevent accidental operation, the wheelchair remained in an idle state until a predefined activation sequence—referred to as the start pattern—was detected. This pattern was fully customizable by the user; for example, a sequence such as right → left → right could be defined during setup. The system continuously compared the incoming stream of classified gaze states against the stored pattern and transitioned into active-control mode only when a complete match occurred within a set time window.

Figure 6. Annotated photograph of the completed eye-controlled wheelchair system showing the user wearing the custom EOG glasses, with arrows indicating the 3D-printed glasses frame, the lateral dry electrodes, and the motorized wheelchair platform.

A universal safety mechanism was implemented for stopping the wheelchair. Regardless of the current mode, the detection of three or more rapid blinks within one second triggered an immediate stop. This stop condition was intentionally chosen because rapid blinking is both easy to perform voluntarily and naturally occurs in situations where continued wheelchair motion would be unsafe—for example, if dust, debris, or an eyelash enters the user’s eye, causing an involuntary series of quick blinks, the wheelchair would automatically halt, ensuring that visual obstruction cannot lead to uncontrolled movement.

2.7 Data Collection and Statistical Methods

Data collection focused on evaluating the accuracy of the system’s horizontal eye-movement classification. EOG signals were recorded in real time while a synchronized video of the user’s face was captured to provide a ground-truth reference for gaze direction. During a controlled session, the user also performed a series of intentional left and right eye movements at regular intervals. The video was later reviewed manually, and each intentional movement was annotated with its corresponding timestamp.

The continuous EOG recording was segmented into fixed-length samples of 0.5 seconds (37 data points per segment at 75 Hz). Each segment was assigned a ground-truth label—left, right, or neutral—based on the video annotations. The algorithm’s predicted label for each sample was then compared against the ground truth to determine classification correctness, and accuracy was computed as the proportion of correctly classified samples out of the total number of labeled samples.

Results

3.1 Signal Interpretation Accuracy

A total of 394 labeled EOG segments were evaluated against the classifier’s output. Of these, 351 segments were correctly identified, resulting in an overall classification accuracy of 89.1%. Accuracy was computed as the proportion of correctly classified samples relative to the total number of labeled segments. No additional weighting or post-processing adjustments were applied.

3.2 Cost Effectiveness

Component	Cost (USD)
Manual wheelchair	\$120.00
Wheelchair electronics	\$137.00
Mechanical parts	\$40.00
Glasses frame (3D-printed)	\$0.15
Glasses electronics	\$26.00
Ag/AgCl electrodes	\$4.00
Total Cost	\$327.15

Table 1. Total material cost for the complete prototype, including wheelchair motorization hardware and the VisionLens EOG acquisition device.

3.3 Additional System Performance Metrics

Several secondary performance metrics were evaluated to assess the system's overall functionality, usability, and engineering robustness. The prototype demonstrated:

- 0.62 s mean processing delay from signal acquisition to motor activation
- 134 g total weight of the VisionLens headband
- 9 hr 34 min theoretical battery life for the wearable device
- 0.40–0.50 mph stable wheelchair operating speed
- Non-invasive dry Ag/AgCl electrodes, requiring no conductive gel or skin preparation

Discussion

This study evaluated a non-invasive EOG-based control interface for powered wheelchair navigation, with the aim of determining whether low-cost dry electrodes and lightweight electronics could support reliable, real-time mobility control. The system achieved 89% classification accuracy, sub-second processing delay, stable wheelchair motion, and multi-hour wearability, supporting the original hypothesis that an accessible and affordable eye-controlled mobility platform is feasible. These findings align with the performance expectations defined at the outset of the study and demonstrate that horizontal EOG signals can serve as an effective input modality for hands-free assistive control.

Compared with prior work, the system's performance is consistent with reported accuracy ranges for EOG-based classifiers while relying on fewer electrodes and simpler hardware. Earlier

prototypes often depended on wet electrodes, multi-channel amplification, or strict environmental conditions, whereas the glasses-mounted dry-electrode configuration used here improved comfort, reduced setup time, and preserved signal quality sufficient for real-time control. These results suggest broader implications for assistive mobility technologies: specifically, that low-cost, non-invasive biosignal systems may serve as practical alternatives to commercial eye-tracking solutions, which typically require more complex hardware and higher cost barriers.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. Evaluation was performed with a single user, limiting generalizability to clinical populations, and the control scheme incorporated only horizontal eye movements, restricting the available command vocabulary. EOG signals remain sensitive to baseline drift and motion artifacts, which may influence long-term stability. Future work should therefore include multi-user testing, expanded command sets, improved adaptive filtering, and integration of safety features such as autonomous braking or obstacle detection. Overall, the results support the feasibility of a low-cost EOG-based control interface for powered mobility and reinforce its potential to increase independence for individuals with severe motor impairments.

Conclusion

This study set out to determine whether a low-cost, non-invasive EOG-based interface could reliably control a powered wheelchair for individuals with severe motor impairments. The prototype met this objective, demonstrating high classification accuracy, real-time responsiveness, stable wheelchair motion, and multi-hour wearable operation using inexpensive dry electrodes and lightweight electronics. These findings indicate that accessible, affordable eye-controlled mobility systems are technically feasible and can offer meaningful alternatives to traditional joystick interfaces and commercially available eye-tracking technologies.

Future work may incorporate multi-directional commands, improved drift compensation, safety features such as obstacle avoidance, and clinical evaluation with individuals who have Motor Neuron Disease. Overall, this research highlights the potential of low-cost biopotential interfaces to increase autonomy and improve quality of life for users with severe motor limitations.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank **Preserve Physical Therapy Clinic** for providing the wheelchair used in the development of this prototype. The author also acknowledges **Upside Down Labs** for making the open-source BioAmp EXG hardware and documentation available, which supported the signal acquisition system. This project received no external funding.

Works Cited

Barrett, Kim E., and William F. Ganong. *Ganong's Review of Medical Physiology*. 26th ed., McGraw-Hill, 2019.

Barea, Rafael, et al. "System for Assisted Mobility Using Eye Movements Based on Electrooculography." *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 4, 2002, pp. 209–218.

Berry, Richard B., et al. *The AASM Manual for the Scoring of Sleep and Associated Events: Rules, Terminology and Technical Specifications. Version 3.0*, American Academy of Sleep Medicine, 2023.

Brown, Robert H., and Ammar Al-Chalabi. "Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis." *The New England Journal of Medicine*, vol. 377, no. 2, 2017, pp. 162–172.

Chi, Yu Ming, et al. "Dry-Contact and Noncontact Biopotential Electrodes: Methodological Review." *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 3, 2010, pp. 106–119.

Ferree, Thomas C., et al. "Scalp Electrode Impedance, Infection Risk, and EEG Data Quality." *Clinical Neurophysiology*, vol. 112, no. 3, 2001, pp. 536–544.

Leitgeb, Norbert, et al. "Eye Movement–Based Human–Machine Interface Using Electrooculography." *Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing*, vol. 41, 2003, pp. 164–171.

Picerno, Pietro, et al. "Characterization of Blink-Related EOG Artifacts." *Medical Engineering & Physics*, vol. 30, no. 10, 2008, pp. 1374–1382.

van der Woude, Lucas H. V., et al. "Manual Wheelchairs: Research and Innovation in Rehabilitation, Sports, Daily Life and Health." *Medical Engineering & Physics*, vol. 63, 2018, pp. 1–4.